

CONSUMER'S PERCEPTION AND BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE FOOD PURCHASING

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Abstract

According to Research, India Online Food Delivery Market will be US\$ 21.41 Billion by 2026. There is a lot more chance in the Indian online food sector for new companies who are targeting definite demographics. The major players in online food delivery segment are: Swiggy, Zomato, Dominos, KFC and Pizza Hut etc. They offer a wide product choice to consumers and offer a range of features based on quality, price, and value for money. Hence, it becomes essential to study the consumer perception and behaviour towards online food purchasing. The objectives of the study were to study Socio-Economic status of respondents in Chaka block of Prayagraj district, to determine consumer perception and behaviour, to study the factors influencing online food purchasing and to identify the problems affecting online food purchasing. The research was done by collecting primary data with the help of questionnaires. The questionnaire was aimed at the analysis of various variables that affect the buying decision of online food. The sample sizes were 120 respondents from Prayagraj district. Five-point Likert scale technique was used to collect the data collection. The collected data were analyzed using Perceptual mapping, Standard deviation and Garette Ranking technique. Better discount and better choice of restaurants has gained positive opinion of majority of the consumers in comparison to other attributes. The major constraints faced by the consumers during the purchase of online food were food items are not easily refundable and late delivery followed by poor quality, range of delivery, inadequate quantity and delivered food is different than ordered food.

Keywords: - Consumer decision, perception, attitudes, research, online food purchasing.

Introduction

The online food ordering is a concept that every restaurant is using to facilitate their customers with improved services. Lots of individuals would favour to spend their free time going out with friends and families to different exotic or exclusive restaurants but there are some events within which they'd opt to get the food at their doorstep because again and again people don't prefer to move out in crowded places so that they favour to order food online. The Online Food Ordering System is well-defined as a straightforward and suitable way for purchasers to buy food online, without having to travel to the restaurant. Online food ordering is enabled by the internet – it's the network that connects the restaurant or the company on one hand, and also the customer on other hand. Therefore, as per this technique, the customer visits the app or website, browses through the varied food items, combos and cuisines available there and goes ahead and selects and purchases the things he or she needs. The application updates the user about the expected duration of food preparation and delivery. These things will then be delivered to the customer at his or her doorstep at the time they choose by a delivery person. Payments for such online orders is made through debit cards, credit cards, cash or card on delivery, or perhaps through digital wallets or UPI. Online food delivery is totally safe and secure. These features, in convergence with attributes like ease, speed and precision of delivery, are increasing the demand for these services in India.

Therefore, the service of online delivering food from any place to any other place has given rise to some very popular Start-Ups like Zomato, Swiggy, and Uber Eats. These Apps offer a direct contrast between the prices and ratings of different restaurants serving the same dishes and allow you to make a decision based on these options or choices.

Food Apps is broadly classified into three categories –

1) Fully integrated – Apps who process food and delivers.

Ex – Dominos, MacDonald's, etc.

2) Delivery as a service.

3) Aggregators – These apps provide a platform for customers where they could discover restaurants, and navigate through menus of different cuisines and select the food. In short, aggregates information about for the customers and function as an order generating a channel for restaurants. Ex. Swiggy, Zomato, food panda, etc

Some major players in India are-

1. Zomato
2. Swiggy
3. Food panda
4. Kfc

5. Domino's pizza

Research Methodology

Sampling procedure- Multistage graded random sampling procedure was adopted for the present study to select the ultimate unit of the sample. The Selection of District, block, villages and respondents were done randomly.

Stage 1: Selection of the district – There are total 75 districts in Uttar Pradesh from which Prayagraj district was selected purposively to study about the consumer's perception and buying behavior towards online food purchasing

Stage 2: Selection of block - The second stage of sampling is Selection of the block. Out of 23 blocks present in Prayagraj districts, Chaka block was selected purposively.

Stage 3: Selection of villages- There are total 137 villages in Chaka block. The list of the villages of selected block was obtained from the block development office. Then all the villages are arranged in order and 5% villages were selected randomly out of total number of villages.

List of selected villages in Chaka block

1. Mahewa west
2. Chaka
3. Cheonki
4. Dandi
5. Gangotri nagar
6. Mahewa Patti Paschim Uparhar

Stage 4: Selection of Respondents - Respondents were selected from these six villages of chaka block. 20 Respondents were randomly selected from each village. Total 120 respondents were selected for the study.

Standard deviation:

The standard deviation is defined as the deviation of the values or data from an average mean.

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum |x - \bar{x}|^2}{n}}$$

where,

σ = Standard Deviation
 x = each of the values of the Data
 \bar{x} = Mean
 n = Total number of data points

Likert Scale:

A Likert scale is a rating scale used to assess opinions attitudes, or behaviours. Likert scale are popular in survey research because they allow us to easily operationalise personality trade or perception.

To collect data of present participants with Likert type question or statement and a continuum of possible responses, usually with 5 or 7 items. Each item is given a numerical score so that the data can be analyse quantitatively.

A Likert scale assumes that the strength or intensity of an attitude is linear, i.e. on a continuum from strongly agree to strongly disagree, and makes the assumption that attitudes can be measured.

1	2	3	4	5
Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree

Results And Discussion

Consumers perception and behaviour towards online food purchasing

An attempt was made to elicit the factors considered by the respondents for purchase of food online in prayagraj district.

Time since consumers use online food delivery

Out of total 120 consumers surveyed, 14% i.e. (17 respondents) of the consumers buying online food online from less than one year, 29% i.e. (35 respondents) buying food online from one to three years, 38% i.e. (45 respondents) buying food online from three to five years and 19% i.e. (23 respondents) buying food online from more than five years

S.No	Time since consumer using online food delivery	Number	Percentage
1	Less than 1 year	17	14.16%
2	1-3 year	35	29.16%
3	3-5 year	45	37.5%
4	More than 5 years	23	19.16%

Therefore, Standard deviation of this given table is 10.81

Sources of information

If we consider the source of information, friends and relatives had create a great impact on consumers mind related to awareness of online food purchasing and advertisement also had played an important role in creating awareness about online food delivery among the consumers.

It was found that out of 120 respondents 5.83% get to know about online food purchasing from their spouse, 16.66% get to know about online food purchasing from their children, 13.33% get to know about online food purchasing from their parents, 29.16% get to know about online food purchasing from their friends and relatives and 35% get to know about online food purchasing from the advertisement.

S.No	Source of Information	Number	Percentage
1	Spouse	7	5.83%
2	Children	20	16.66%
3	Parents	16	13.33%
4	Friends and Relatives	35	29.16%
5	Advertisement	42	35%

Frequency of purchase

Out of 120 respondents 25 respondents buy food online once in a week, 41 respondents buy food online twice in a week, 27 respondents buy food online more than twice in a week, 19

respondents buy food online once in a month and 10 respondents buy food online once in a few months. Most of the consumers buy food online only one time in a week.

Therefore, Standard deviation of this given table is 12.75.

S.No	Frequency of online food purchasing	Number	Percentage
1	once in a week	25	20.833%
2	twice in a week	41	34.16%
3	More than twice in a week	27	22.5%
4	once in a month	19	15.83%
5	once in a few months	10	8.33%

Therefore, Standard deviation of this given table is 10.19.

Expenditure of online food purchasing

Total amount spent by consumers in a month on online food purchasing is given below in the chart. Out of 120 respondents 30 people spend less than 500 rupees in a month on online food, 45

people spend between 500 to 2000 rupees in a month on online food, 33 people spend between 2000 to 4000 rupees in a month on online food and 12 people spend more than 4000 rupees in a month on online food purchasing.

S.No	Expenditure	Number	Percentage
1	Less than 500 Rs	30	25%
2	500-2000 Rs	45	37.5%
3	2000-4000 RS	33	27.5%
4	More than 4000 Rs	12	10%

Therefore, Standard deviation of this given table is 11.81

Analyse factors influencing online food purchasing

In this research Factor analysis was used to determine which factors influence online food purchasing. The Likert scale is a five-point scale that is used to allow an individual to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement.

The Likert scale provides five possible answers to a statement or question that allows respondents to indicate their positive-to-negative strength of agreement or strength of feeling regarding the question or statement.

Likert scale has been used to analyse the factors that influence online food purchasing.

SA: Strongly Agree (5), A: Agree (4), N: Neutral (3), DA: Disagree (2), SDA: Strongly Disagree (1)

Statements regarding online food purchasing	SA (5)	A (4)	N (3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	Total
Service quality	6	5	7	9	3	30
On time delivery	3	5	2	6	7	23
Better choice of restaurants	6	7	4	10	4	31
Online food purchasing gives me better discount	8	6	11	4	7	36

Conclusion

With the constant inflow of population and rapid development in India, the food delivery and restaurant segment are now flourishing at a blistering pace due to which there is a successful increase in the use of Smartphones and food apps. Due to the busy and hectic timetable of every individual's, online food purchasing has now become a life-saving part of their life.

This study shows the relationship between factors and attributes which is considered to be important for the satisfaction of the customer while ordering food from these online food delivery apps. It is also found that ease of availability of the desired food at any time and at the same time easy access to internet are the prime reasons for using the online food delivery services. This study reveals that the delivery time of food items is the most important attribute while the usability of the app is the least responsible for the satisfaction of the customer. The Study was conducted to know how satisfied are the consumers with the online food delivery services and what is their basic perception of it and what are the problems they face while ordering food online. The study brought various conclusions about how much satisfied are people with the online food delivery. Most of the people want restaurants to provide on time delivery and packaging of food is quite important for consumers. This study also helps to know the perception of the consumers about online food purchasing which helps the restaurants to identify the dishes which are most preferred by the consumers and about their likes and dislikes. This also helps to know about the factors which influence the consumer behavioural intention towards online food delivery services.

Major Findings

Majority of the respondents were influenced by advertisement to prefer online food purchasing.

Most of the respondents purchase food online through apps like Swiggy, Zomato, etc.

Most of the respondents order food online at least twice a week.

Most of the respondents purchase online food because it saves time, wider variety of restaurants presents in the apps.

Most of the respondents were satisfied by the discounts provided by the restaurants and the ratings which helps in better choice of restaurants.

Majority of the respondents were satisfied with the service quality provided by online food purchasing.

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